

OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE AND TARO YAMANE SAMPLING METHOD: THE PARADIGM SHIFT

Oluyemi Ayodele OLONITE

Email: oluyemiolonite@hotmail.com

Mobile No: +2347062205843

Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2785-2337>

Research Gate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Oluyemi-Olonite-2>

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INTRODUCTION

The Olonite Sampling Technique is a sampling method that is used for small and large population. It was developed as a solution to the short comings of the Taro Yamane Sampling Technique. OST ranges from “1 – 1,280,000,000 (one - one billion two hundred and eighty million) population” and 1 - 59,500, having two (2) categories with five (5) versions each. OST asserts that for some set of levels of significance, a particular category and version of sampling formulae should be adopted; level of significance 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.2, 0.01, 0.002 and 0.001 should focus on the category 1 and use the total population to know the version to be considered. For level of significance 0.4, 0.3, and 0.2, the category 2 should be considered and the total population should be used to determine the version to be considered. The Olonite Sampling Technique supports the 2/3 rule to a logical extent. Taro Yamane Sampling Method can only be used for populations below “four hundred (400)” and using Taro Yamane for a population above 400 might not give us a result closer to reality as the half value will not be attained using the Taro Yamane Sampling Technique but the Olonite Sampling Technique.

Keywords: Olonite, Sampling, Technique, Taro, Yamane, Population

Table 1: Olonite Sampling Technique formulae table

VERSIONS	CATEGORY 1	CATEGORY 2
	For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001	For Level of Significance: 0.4, 0.3 & 0.2
Version 1:	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ For population ranging between 1 – 8,000	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ For population ranging between 1 – 1,550
Version 2:	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^4}$ For population ranging between 8001 – 160,000	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^4}$ For population ranging between 1,551 – 3.665
Version 3:	$SS = \frac{TP}{TP}$	$SS = \frac{TP}{TP}$

	$1 + \frac{TP(TCL - OCL)^5}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^5}$ For population ranging between 160,001 – 3,200,000	$1 + \frac{TP(TCL - OCL)^5}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^5}$ For population ranging between 3,666 – 9,400
Version 4:	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^6}$ For population ranging between 3,200,001 – 64,000,000	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^6}$ For population ranging between 9,401 – 23,500
Version 5:	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^7}$ For population ranging between 64,000,001 – 1,280,000,000	$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^7}$ For population ranging between 23,501 – 59,500
<p>Note: SS = Sampling Size TP = Total Population 1 = Booster or Step-down μ = Stochastic Error $^{3-7}$ = Multiplier TCL = Total Confidence Level OCL = Observed Confidence Level</p>		

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

CATEGORY 1, VERSIONS 1

Table 2: Category 1, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.15	75	31
2.	1,280,000,000	0.15	585,009,140	44,444

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 3: Category 1, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.1	91	50
2.	1,280,000,000	0.1	9,922,480	99,999

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 4: Category 1, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.05	99	80
2.	1,280,000,000	0.05	640,000,000	399,999,875

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 5: Category 1, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.02	100	96
2.	1,280,000,000	0.02	1,277,906,278	2,450

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 6: Category 1, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.01	100	99
2.	1,280,000,000	0.01	1,279,983,616	9,999

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 7: Category 1, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.002	100	96
2.	1,280,000,000	0.002	1,280,000,000	249,951

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 8: Category 1, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.001	100	99
2.	1,280,000,000	0.001	1,280,000,000	999,219

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

CATEGORY 2, VERSION 1

Table 9: Category 2, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.2	56	20

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 10: Category 2, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.3	55	10

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 11: Category 2, Version 1

S/N	POPULATION	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	
			OLONITE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE	TARO YAMANE METHOD
1.	100	0.4	71	9

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

Table 2 – 11 above show that it is only the Olonite Sampling Technique that support the 2/3 rule to a reasonable extent for the significance level 0.15, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001.

The higher the Multiplier, the higher the sample size, however, this claim is to a specific extent because when the multiplier reaches a certain level, the diminishing the sample size becomes.

For the full sampling size selection for each observed confidence level and population, check the **“Olonite Sampling Table”**.